

PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF PRODUCTION IN THE INDUSTRY

Goimov A.N.

Graduate student of Termiz University of Economics and Service

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Abstract. *Rational organization of the country's economy is one of the important directions of economic policy. Effective use of the natural, economic and labor potential of the regions is one of the main conditions for achieving economic independence and ensuring economic growth, improving the living standards of the population of our country. This article provides information about the prospects for the development of production in the industry.*

Keywords: *industry, development of the industrial network, development of export potential, economic growth, capital and scientific-technical development, market reforms.*

Introduction of systematic democratic market reforms, further deepening of economic liberalization processes, consistent implementation of structural changes in industrial sectors, continuation of modernization and diversification processes are the main factors of Uzbekistan's success. The continuous growth of the country's gross domestic product is not due to the traditional raw materials industries or the favorable conditions in the world market, the high prices of some raw materials and materials, but on the contrary, it is provided due to the rapid and priority development of the production of competitive finished products and modern service industries.

In general, industry is one of the main sectors of the economy of our republic. Because the industry is fundamentally different from other sectors and sectors with its added value creation, its role in meeting the needs of the population and its high-level production locomotive. The development of the industrial network leads to the development of the national economy at a steady pace. Processes of diversification will be improved due to processing of all resources mined and cultivated in the field of industry, production of new products from them, increase of assortment and nomenclature.

As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan M. Sh. Mirziyoev noted, "as a result of systemic changes in the economy, the share of industry in the structure of the gross domestic product is expected to increase from 35 percent to 37 percent this year. However, in some cities and districts, this very important issue is not given enough attention.

As a result, the share of industry in 27 districts of the republic does not even reach 1% of the regional indicator. Therefore, it is necessary to develop medium and long-term programs for the development of the industry of each district and city. First of all, the leaders of the Republic of Karakalpakstan and the regions should take special control of this issue"[1].

According to preliminary data, in 2018, 228.9 trillion were spent by the republic's enterprises. Soum industrial products were produced, the growth rate compared to the corresponding period of last year was 114.4%, and the industrial production index was 110.6%.

The main factor in the growth of total industrial production is 13.2% of production in the manufacturing industry, 25.4% in mining and open-pit mining, 4.1% in the supply of electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning. % and increase of water supply, sewage system, waste disposal by -22.6%.

Industry is one of the main branches of the national product production of our country. The industry is fundamentally different from other sectors and sectors with its added value creation, its role in meeting the needs of the population, and its high level of production capabilities. Industry is the main and leading branch of material production, and its development leads to the development of the national economy at a steady pace.

To further increase the efficiency and competitiveness of the industry based on the rapid and sustainable development of the industrial sectors of our country, the growth of their export potential, the technical and technological re-equipment of production enterprises, the supply of the domestic market with products produced in national enterprises, the effective use of existing resources, and the implementation of an active investment policy. can be achieved.

In this regard, as a result of the priority industrial development program adopted in our country in 2011-2015 and the consistent implementation of industry programs for modernization of production, technical and technological renewal, the role of processing industries producing competitive products with high added value in the structure of the industry is increasing. Today, more than 78 percent of the industrial products produced in our country are accounted for by these industries. It is known that economic growth in the industry is directly dependent on such factors as labor, capital and scientific and technical progress. The level of correlation between labor and capital factors of economic growth is high. In the past period, structural shifts occurred in our country as a result of changes in the volume of industrial production, the volume of investments involved in the industry, and the number of people employed in the sector.

In January-December 2018, the volume of products produced by the mining industry and open-pit mines amounted to 36.9 trillion soums, or 16.1% of the total volume of industrial products.

Investment activity in industry has been unstable over the past period, with industry's share of capital accumulation and total domestic investment increasing until 2018 and then declining sharply until 2000, with only a slight improvement from 2012. Such a change in the development of the national industry is explained by the decrease in the price of cotton and rare metals and, accordingly, by the decrease in the foreign trade balance, in particular, export earnings.

The national industry and its sectors are dynamically changing sectors of the economy with rapidly increasing production rates. In particular, the volume of production in the ferrous metallurgy, oil and petrochemical, machine building, construction materials, light and food industries has been growing rapidly in recent years.

In particular, in 2000-2013, the average annual additional growth rate was 14.5 percent in ferrous metallurgy, about 3.0 percent in non-ferrous metallurgy, 8.1 percent in chemistry and petrochemicals, 18 percent in engineering, 9.8 percent in light industry, and food industry. It was 9.4 percent. In general, the rate of annual additional growth of industrial production was 7-8 percent on average in these years. In the conditions of modernization of the economy, in the period of deep structural changes and economic reforms in our country, there are opportunities for more rapid development of industrial production, especially in the fields of light, fuel and energy, chemical and petrochemical, food and machinery.

We think it is necessary to pay attention to the following principles when determining directions for the activation of industrial production in the region:

- focus on industrial enterprises that meet market demand. This means granting and supporting enterprises depending on their ownership form: that is, first of all (known from foreign

experience) private enterprises, foreign enterprises, joint enterprises, open shareholder societies. Enterprises based on these properties should be seen as the main driving force behind regional economic development.

- to increase the level of utilization of existing production capacities in our country;
- restoration of production capacities that are stopped today;
- activation of communication with existing company managers. To study and analyze the capabilities of the companies they lead and to support processes related to diversification of production, acquisition of new technologies, opportunities to work with foreign partners, production of import-substituting goods, participation in localization programs, and cooperation.
 - building a new material and technical base;
- attraction of investment projects aimed at production of competitive and export-oriented products based on new technology to small industrial zones in the region.
 - creation of favorable conditions for the activity of newly established enterprises;
- studying the production activities of small businesses, private enterprises in the region, identifying promising businesses, and supporting them, especially entrepreneurs who have the opportunity to produce exportable products;
 - to further increase the number of small enterprises in the development of the industrial network and encourage measures for their organization;
 - rapid development of the localization program aimed at the production of import-substituting finished products.

Each region should define its regional industrial policy. The regional industrial policy is a system of measures aimed at the economic development of this region, it aims to modernize the processing industry that creates high added value on the basis of high technologies, to stimulate the innovative development of small business and private entrepreneurship in the industrial sector, to strengthen cooperation between industrial enterprises, and to attract foreign investments to the region. and strengthening cooperation with them, aimed at developing the concept of complex development of priority sectors of the industrial sector and the development of a complex development program will serve to set the industrial development in the region on the right track and accelerate it.

REFERENCES

1. 2017 йилда қабул қилинган “Ўзбекистон республикасини ривожлантиришнинг 5 та устувор йўналиш бўйича Ҳаракатлар стратегияси” нинг 3- йўналиши 3.2 ва 3.5 бандлари.
2. “Кичик саноат зоналарини барпо этиш ва уларнинг фаолиятини ташкил қилиш тартиби тўғрисидаги низомни тасдиқлаш ҳақида”ги Ўзбекистон Республикаси Вазирлар Маҳкамасининг 2014 йил 31 декабрь, 378 – сонли қарори.
3. Кузнецова С. Н., Кузнецов В. П. Методика оценки интегральной эффективности инвестиционных проектов в рамках промышленных парков: монография / Мининский университет. Нижний Новгород. 2015. 200 с.
4. Porter M. E. On competition. Cambridge. MA: A Harvard Business Review Book. 1998.
5. Х.Набиев, Д.Набиев. Иқтисодий статистика. – Т.:ТДИУ, 2009.
6. Фуломов С.С. Тадбиркорлик ва кичик бизнес.-Т.: Шарк, 2002.-183б.